

PELATIHAN KARYA TULIS ILMIAH DESA BINAAN ULM BERDAMPAK

MERDEKA BELAJAR KAMPUS MERDEKA

UNIVERSITAS LAMBUNG
MANGKURAT

by

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PROFIL

- Prodi Tadris Fisika UIN Antasari Banjarmasin
- S3 Pendidikan IPA jalur Penelitian UNS 2025 s.d Sekarang
- Editor in Chief Tarbiyah: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan (Sinta 2 dan DOAJ)
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INTRODUCTION

- Karya Tulis Ilmiah terbagi menjadi 3 jenis:
 1. Karya tulis penelitian (Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, RnD, Mixed Method)
 2. Karya Tulis Studi Pustaka (SLR, Bibliometric)
 3. Karya Tulis Pengabdian kepada Masyarakat
- Perbedaan paling tampak di metode penelitian jenis karya tulis ilmiah
- Karya tulis pengabdian memiliki perbedaan dengan “LAPORAN PENGABDIAN kepada MASYARAKAT”
- Karya tulis pengabdian tetap sistematis dan memiliki research gap serta novelty
- <https://journal.ugm.ac.id/jpkm/article/view/91162/42576>
- Judul Community Empowerment in Organic Waste Management in The Tourist Village of Batudema The Tourist Villages of Batumadeg and Batukandik Nusa Penida Bali

INTRODUCTION

- Karya tulis ilmiah pengabdian merupakan bentuk artikel berupa kegiatan yang masyarakat melibatkan penerapan pengetahuan, keterampilan, dan teknologi terkait di berbagai bidang dan memiliki berdampak positif pada kehidupan masyarakat (Irawan et al, 2023)
- Model Pendekatan karya tulis ilmiah yang dituliskan untuk pengabdian kepada masyarakat
 1. Penyuluhan
 2. Model Pelatihan
 3. Pengembangan teknologi tepat guna
 4. Penerapan inovasi sosial

ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

- Artikel Desa Binaan jenis artikel pengabdian masyarakat yang berisi IMRAD (Introduction, Method, Result, Analysis and Discussion) (Rusli et al, 2024)
- Artikel Desa Binaan menggambarkan kegiatan yang dilakukan di tempat desa binaan disesuaikan dengan IMRAD
- Contoh judul artikel desa binaan:
 1. Kegiatannya pemanfaatan komersil durian bisa dibuat judul "Pemanfaatan Nilai Konsumsi Durian sebagai Pengembangan Komoditi Desa Pait Kabupaten Malang"
 2. Kegiatan penyuluhan stunting bisa dibuat judul " Penyuluhan Gizi Anak sebagai Pencegahan Stunting"

INTRODUCTION ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

- Introduction artikel Desa Binaan berisi gambaran desa secara deskriptif. Sumber daya yang dimiliki dan bagaimana memanfaatkan. Contohnya penghasil duren, penghasil kayu manis dan sumber daya lainnya.
- Introduction artikel Desa Binaan berisi gambaran kehidupan sosial masyarakat dan apa yang akan dimanfaatkan, sebagai bagian dari desa berdampak. Contohnya belum memiliki Karang Taruna, masyarakat masih sekolah tingkat dasar dan masalah sosial lainnya untuk dibantu solusi.
- Introduction berisi bagaimana seharusnya memaksimalkan sumber daya dan masalah yang sesuai dengan kondisi yang dihadapi di lapangan

METHOD ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

- Method artikel Desa Binaan disesuaikan dengan metode pengabdian kepada masyarakat (Afandi, 2022)
1. Participatory Action Research (PAR)
 - Pendekatan penelitian partisipatif di mana masyarakat terlibat aktif dalam mengidentifikasi dan menyelesaikan masalah. Contohnya kegiatan penyuluhan, pembelajaran kewirausahaan dan lain-lain
 2. Asset Based Community Development (ABCD)
 - Pendekatan yang berfokus pada pengenalan dan penguatan aset-aset yang ada dalam komunitas untuk meningkatkan kualitas hidup. Contohnya buah duren melimpah kemudian dijual buah, bisa dilatih untuk pemanfaatan cake, kulitnya untuk pupuk kompos dan lain-lain

METHOD ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

3. Community Participatory Research

- Pendekatan penelitian yang melibatkan kolaborasi antara para peneliti dan masyarakat dalam seluruh proses penelitian. Contohnya kegiatan PKK bersama tokoh masyarakat kemudian mengembangkan kewirausahaan.

4. Service Learning (SL)

- Pendekatan pendidikan yang melibatkan mahasiswa dalam memberikan pelayanan kepada masyarakat sebagai bagian dari pembelajaran. Contohnya memberikan penyuluhan gizi, belajar mengaji, belajar tambahan siswa sekolah dan lain-lain.

RESULT ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

Result artikel Desa Binaan berisi hasil kegiatan yang telah dilakukan

PENGANTAR METODOLOGI PENGABDIAN MASYARAKAT 91162-412607-1-PB

survey in Batumadeg village, Nusa Penida. The KKN team used three basic questions as analytical instruments. These questions involve how waste is processed at TOSS Batumadeg, the daily routine of waste officers at that location, and the waste collection process, which then undergoes further sorting and processing.

Based on these three questions, local citizens—Mrs. Kadek and Mrs. Tri Diani—explained that waste sorting activities had so far been categorized only into organic and inorganic waste. Some of the waste had been directly processed at TOSS, while the remaining portions had been sent to the Nusa Penida TPA. When asked about waste processing activities, they further explained that the primary focus had been on converting organic waste into compost as highlighted by Sudaryatno et al., (2024).

Regarding the waste collection process, they stated that collection had taken place on Tuesdays and Fridays at 8 a.m. in Batumadeg Village, ensuring even waste transportation from the Tembeling tourist area to the local village office. The discussion and interview process took place near the Batumadeg Village Office, involving 13 participants—an increase from the previous year when only 10 people had participated. From these interviews, the KKN Team concluded that the local community demonstrated environmental awareness and had successfully formulated and implemented solutions for waste sorting and processing.

In addition to analyzing problems through interviews, the TOSS survey generated innovative ideas, such as creating bottle ornaments at TOSS BTM. These ornaments were intended to inspire public participation in waste management activities. Furthermore, the KKN team created decorative bottle ornaments, promoting environmental awareness and sustainability (Figure 2). The initiative encouraged waste reduction while fostering community engagement by transforming discarded plastic materials into creative and functional art pieces. The project also served as an educational tool, inspiring local residents and tourists to adopt eco-friendly practices. Ultimately, this effort supported environmental conservation and contributed to the development of sustainable livelihoods for the local community (Budiarto et al., 2023; Sulistiyani et al., 2025).

Figure 2 . The process of making bottle ornaments using plastic waste

This website collects data on garbage points, plantation locations, Balinese cattle farms, cultural information, and tourist destinations (Figure 3). It aims to broaden the reach of information, allowing both the community and tourists

Latifah et al. Community Empowerment in Organic Waste

Figure 3 . Nusa Penida website application

ANALYSIS DISCUSSION ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

Setelah penjelasan dan visualisasi gambar diberikan pembahasan dan diskusi berkaitan denmgan proses yang telah dilakukan artikel Desa Binaan berisi hasil kegiatan yang telah dilakukan

The screenshot displays a PDF document with three browser tabs at the top: 'Daftar Lokal Reguler buat PPL 1', 'PENGANTAR METODOLOGI PENGABDIAN MASYARAKAT', and '91162-412607-1-PB'. The main content area features three photographs labeled 'a', 'b', and 'c'. Panel 'a' shows a group of people, including a man in a military uniform, gathered around a table. Panel 'b' shows a man operating a blue machine. Panel 'c' shows a man pushing a green cart. Below the images is the caption 'Figure 7 . Product eco-enzyme'. The page number '146' and the URL 'www.jurnal.ugm.ac.id/jpkm' are visible. The article title 'Community Empowerment in Organic Waste' and the author 'Latifah et al.' are also present. The text describes the process of creating eco-enzymes from plastic waste and includes a section titled '4. CONCLUSION'.

Figure 7 . Product eco-enzyme

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Latifah et al. Community Empowerment in Organic Waste

tool to create various accessory molds. The process involved several stages, including plastic waste collection, pressing, shredding, melting, and molding.

The Holzewiq tool, named by the KKN Team, was introduced as an innovative device capable of melting plastic waste into solid, durable products in the shape of tubes and hearts. Following the dissemination conducted

4. CONCLUSION

In implementing community empowerment activities focused on waste management in Batumadeg and Batukandik Villages, Nusa Penida, the UGM 2nd Period KKN Nirwana Team was deemed successful, particularly in designing and executing empowerment programs that were

CONCLUSION ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

Kesimpulan dituliskan sesuai hasil yang dilakukan bersama desa binaan dan implikasi terhadap kegiatan desa binaan apa. Jelaskan pada bagian kesimpulan.

4. CONCLUSION

In implementing community empowerment activities focused on waste management in Batumadeg and Batukandik Villages, Nusa Penida, the UGM 2nd Period KKN Nirwana Team was deemed successful, particularly in designing and executing empowerment programs that were educational, aspirational, and responsive to community needs. The high level of enthusiasm observed during dissemination activities—especially among students at SDN 2 and SMPN Satu Atap 1 Batukandik—demonstrated the effectiveness of the KKN Team in delivering essential education on waste management.

Furthermore, through waste processing initiatives such as TOSS surveys, the production of eco-enzymes from organic waste, and the use of the Holzewiq tool to process plastic waste, the KKN Team successfully converted approximately 5 kg of inorganic waste into more eco-friendly products. The active participation of the community in these activities highlighted the significant potential for fostering long-term behavioral change in waste management practices. Therefore, it is hoped that community service initiatives, such as the Community Service Program (KKN), will continue to be implemented sustainably, ensuring a lasting positive impact on communities across Indonesia.

KESIMPULAN ARTIKEL DESA BINAAN

1. Artikel desa binaan bukan menuliskan laporan atau cerita proses pembinaan yang telah dilakukan tetapi lebih pada sisi ilmiah artikel
2. Sisi ilmiah artikel meliputi introduction berisi gap penelitian, metode pengabdian berisi metode kegiatan pengabdian seperti apa, hasil bagaimana dan diskusi seperti apa serta kesimpulan.
3. Artikel desa binaan menimbulkan dampak publikasi ilmiah secara luas dibandingkan berita pelaksanaan desa binaan melalui platform media digital
4. Kumpulan referensi kegiatan desa binaan sebelum menulis artikel desa binaan
5. Kumpulan materi uns.id/KTIBinaDesa

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